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RISK OF CHILDREN EXPOSURE TO MERCURY THROUGH OMEGA-3 FATTY ACID FOOD SUPPLEMENTS

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Introduction: Along with significant beneficial health effects of omega-3 fatty acids (FA), health risk associated with potential presence of toxic compounds in omega-3 FA rich sources has to be considered, especially in case of the most susceptible consumers, such as children. The objective of this study was to assess the risk of children exposure to mercury (Hg) through omega-3 FA supplements.

Materials and methods: Twelve omega-3 FA supplements intended for children (4 plant and 8 fish oils) were collected from the markets of Republic of Serbia and Republic of Srpska and subjected to direct mercury analysis. Risk assessment was based on the recommended dosage of supplements and Hg toxicological profile: oral reference dose (RfD) of 0.0001/0.0003 mg/kg bw/day and tolerable weekly intake (TWI) of 0.0013/0.004 mg/kg bw for methyl Hg (MeHg)/inorganic Hg (iHg), former present in fish and latter in plant oils.

Results: Low Hg content resulted with rather low Hg exposure through supplement consumption. Exposure of infants to iHg ranged from 0.01-0.1% of RfD and 0.004-0.5% of TWI, while MeHg exposure was 0.22% of RfD and 0.12% of TWI. Similar exposure levels were obtained for 1 and 2-3 year old children, while in case of children of age 4-10 exposure to MeHg reached the highest level, slightly surpassing 1% of RfD, *i.e.*, 0.6% of TWI. Exposure levels of adolescents were up to 0.61% of RfD and 0.33% of TWI for MeHg.

Conclusion: Hg levels recorded in both fish and plant oil omega-3 FA supplements do not pose concern related to extremely harmful developmental neurotoxicity of MeHg. However, potential presence of other lipophilic environmental pollutants such as polychlorinated compounds in fishes could be a legitimate concern.

Keywords: children health, mercury, fish oil, food supplement

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